

REGULATORY OVERVIEW OF DATA PROTECTION IN WEST AFRICAN ANGLOPHONE COUNTRIES

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Bolt Holdings OU v Circuit Court of Ghana

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Nigeria Data Protection Commission v Meta Platforms LLC

Nigeria Data Protection Commission v Multichoice Nigeria Limited

Nigeria Data Protection Commission v Fidelity Bank Plc

TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS

GDPA - Ghana Data Protection Act 2012

AU- African Union

CAR - Compliance Audit Report

DPA - Data Protection Authority

DPC - Data Protection Commission (Ghana)

DPCO - Data Protection Compliance Organisation

DPIA - Data Protection Impact Assessment

ECOWAS - Economic Community of West African States

EU - European Union

FCCPC - Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

ICT - Information and Communication Technology

NDPA - Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023

NDPC - Nigeria Data Protection Commission

NADPA-RAPDP - Network of African Data Protection Authorities

ABSTRACT

In the 90's, there were no data protection regulations in Africa; however, in 2010, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) adopted a regional Data Protection Regulation, which obligated its member states to establish national data protection laws.¹ As a result, over 37 of 54 African states have enacted comprehensive data protection legislation, indicating an ongoing trend toward legislative convergence.² Government agencies have also acknowledged the need to protect personal data in a rapidly digitalising world. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), renowned for its comprehensive approach to protecting personal data across the European Union (EU), has inspired similar frameworks in Africa. This study aims to analyse the effectiveness of these regulatory measures and their implications for technology-driven businesses and cross-border digital services in West Africa.

Moreover, the regulation of personal data in Africa varies significantly, with countries adopting different models for cross-border data transfers. This paper presents a comprehensive regulatory analysis of personal data protection across Ghana, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Gambia, and Liberia. The comparative analysis is anchored in explicit evaluative criteria: Adequacy (the extent to which national frameworks sufficiently protect personal data), Enforceability (the capacity of statutory and institutional mechanisms to ensure compliance), and Interoperability (the degree to which statutes facilitate cross-border alignment and cooperation).

RESEARCH SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY

This paper adopts doctrinal legal analysis supported by comparative regulatory review and secondary empirical literature. Each jurisdiction is assessed using a uniform Business Data Compliance Memo. It adopts an analytical methodology that integrates comparative benchmarks to evaluate statutory frameworks, regulatory authority, scope of application, compliance obligations, enforcement mechanisms, and regulatory gaps. The objective is to inform business compliance strategy and contribute to legislative and regulatory reasoning within the African tech law landscape.

¹ Raji M, Wilder D, Ugwuoke V and Bashir M, 'Regional Data Protection Initiatives and Legal Frameworks in Africa' *African Journal on Privacy & Data Protection* vol 2

² Carlos Mureithi, 'The State of Data Protection Legislation in Africa' *TechPolicy.Press* (31 May 2024)

INTRODUCTION

The rapid digitisation of everything, including commerce, public services, private life, social connections, and communication globally and in West Africa, has heightened the availability of data, creating low-friction touchpoints where data can be easily collected, stored, analysed, and managed from routine activities. As this data became readily available, companies expanded their capacity to data warehouses to collect, store, integrate, and analyse it at scale, turning personal data into strategic assets. These strategic shifts increased tremendous exposure to security breaches, enabled a sustainable secondary market of personal data, and amplified the precision with which companies could predict and influence through targeted content and personalisation. Because these harms are not easily noticeable or detectable and are structurally intertwined with data-driven business models, the government had to respond through privacy and data protection regulations to protect citizens, impose constraints, and demand accountability for data collection and usage. According to Makulio¹, Africa began engaging in the Information Privacy conversation due to the influence of the European Directive 95/46/EC, which requires that any transfer of personal data to third-world countries (e.g., African countries) must have an acceptable level of data protection.

The response of states in West Africa is reflected in several statutory enforcements and judicial decisions. For instance, in 2024, Nigeria's Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal upheld a **\$220,000,000** fine initially imposed by the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC) on Meta Platform LLC. This was after its investigation and findings of data protection and privacy violations, particularly in WhatsApp and Facebook services.² The above Tribunal further awarded **\$35,000** to the FCCPC as the legal costs for the investigation. This ruling affirmed the breadth of domestic consumer and data protection norms in Nigeria and across Africa against multinational tech companies. In a related enforcement action, the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) imposed a **\$32,800,000** fine on Meta in February 2025 for alleged violations of the Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA) 2023. The violations included processing data of non-users without consent, failure to file mandatory compliance audits, unauthorised cross-border transfers, and

¹ Alex B Makulilo, 'Data Protection Regimes in Africa: Too Far from the European Adequacy Standard' (2012) *International Data Privacy Law* <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ips031> accessed 14 January 2026.

² Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission v Meta Platforms Inc & WhatsApp LLC

illegally targeting users with behavioural advertising.³ Meta challenged the NDPC's orders but ultimately agreed to negotiate a settlement.

The NDPC also imposed substantial administrative fines against organisations that failed to comply with the national data protection standards mandated by the Act. These include the **₦766,200,000** fine against Multichoice Nigeria Limited for illegal data transfers, and the **₦555,800,000** fine against Fidelity Bank Plc (representing 0.1% of its 2023 revenue) for processing data without consent.⁴ Reports also document judicial awards of damages against companies for data misuse and privacy breaches, with awards reaching multi-million-naira sums in Nigerian courts. For instance, a case in which UBA plc issued a domiciliary account to a bank customer without the customer's consent, breaching the customer's data rights⁵ The court ruled in favour of the plaintiffs. (customer) and awarded the sum of **₦8,000,000** on the grounds that banks have no right to transfer money from one account to another without the customer's prior notice or assent.⁶

In other West African countries, such as Ghana, regulators and courts have similarly acted against unauthorised data use, issuing fines and enforcing compliance. For instance, the Circuit Court ordered Bolt Holdings OU to pay **GHC1,900,000** in compensatory damages after finding that the company's identity verification system failed, allowing a third party to impersonate the claimant on its application software⁷. This constitutes negligence and breach of data under Ghana's Data Protection Act, 2012 (Act 843). Equally, the Data Protection Commission (DPC) fined the same company in June 2024 for violating data users' access and rectification rights and failing to fulfil its compliance obligations under the law. In the context of this legislative review, it is unfortunate that the legislative architectures remain uneven across West Africa, with mature systems in several Anglophone states and growing or non-existent systems in others. These developments reveal increasing accountability across the region. With this goal in mind, Nigeria hosted the 2025 8th edition of the Network of African Data Protection Authorities (NADPA-RAPDP) Conference. This conference featured representatives from over 30 African countries, as well as delegates from Europe, Asia, the Middle East, and the United States, around a common goal: reconciling technological innovation with the protection of fundamental rights in the digital age. For technology-sector actors, compliance analysis must therefore address

³ Nigeria Data Protection Commission v Meta Platforms Inc (Federal High Court, Abuja, (FHC/ABJ/CS/355/2025))

⁴ NDPC Compliance Notice (Nijioni) <https://nijioni.com/the-ndpc-compliance-notice/> accessed 14 January 2026.

⁵ United Bank for Africa v. Mr. S. D. Folarin & Anor (2002) LPELR-7178(CA).

⁶ Ilokson & Co. (Nig.) Ltd v. Union Bank of (Nig) Plc (2007) 6 CLRN 25

⁷ Justice Noah Adade v Bolt Ghana Ltd & Anor C11/003/2023 (Circuit Court, Accra)

lawful processing bases, data subject rights, breach-response obligations, cross-border data transfer controls, enforcement pathways, and sanctions. This paper is a statutory analysis with comparative benchmarks drawn from international standards, such as the EU GDPR, and emerging African frameworks, specifically in Anglophone⁸ West African countries.⁹

1. GHANA

1.1. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Ghana's data rights are governed by the **DPA**.¹⁰ which was enacted to give effect to constitutional privacy protections under **Article 18(2) of the 1992 Constitution**.¹¹ The Act established comprehensive regulations for the processing of personal data across both the public and private sectors, reflecting EU data protection models.¹²

1.2. SCOPE AND DEFINITIONS¹³

A data subject, under the GDPA, is any individual who can be directly or indirectly recognised by a network of interconnected systems, otherwise referred to as an identifier. This data is collected by a data controller who is described in the Act as a person who, either alone, jointly with other persons, or in common with other persons, as a statutory duty, determines the purposes for, and the way, personal data is processed or is to be processed.¹⁴ The regulation defines Data Processing as the collection, recording, organisation, storage, use, disclosure, transmission, and destruction of personal data.¹⁵, whether automated or otherwise.

PERSONAL DATA

Personal data is defined as any information relating to an identifiable natural person, whether processed by a controller or processor, electronically or manually.¹⁶ This includes identifiers such as:

- Name; age; date of birth; gender; home address

⁸ Gambia, Ghana, Liberia, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone

⁹ GDPR (n 2).

¹⁰ Data Protection Act 2012 (Ghana) s 1.

¹¹ Constitution of Ghana 1992 Art 18(2).

¹² Makulilo (n 4).

¹³ Ghana Data Protection Commission, 'Official Publications and Compliance Guidance' <https://www.dataprotection.org.gh> accessed 14 January 2026.

¹⁴ Data Protection Act 2012 (Ghana) s 96.

¹⁵ Ibid s 96.

¹⁶ Ibid s. 96

- Personal e-mail address, IP address, personal telephone number, password, personal identification number (pin);
- National identifiers (e.g., passport data);
- Photograph or video identifiable to a natural person;
- Credit card statements; financial profile, utility bills, customer numbers;
- Employees' salaries and human resources files; trade-union membership
- Product and service preferences; personal or behavioural profile; and personal interests derived from tracking use of internet websites.

It should be noted that the processing of personal data is exempt from the provisions of this Act for the purposes of public order, public safety, public morality, national security, or public interest.¹⁷

SENSITIVE DATA

The Act classifies special personal data to include

- Racial or ethnic origin; sexual orientation.
- Religious or philosophical beliefs; political opinions
- Allegations of criminal conduct; criminal investigation reports
- Medical history; health information; genetic data; disabilities

Processing of sensitive data is prohibited unless specific statutory conditions are satisfied.¹⁸ For instance, this does not apply if the processing of personal data relating to the data subject's religious beliefs is carried out by a religious organisation in respect of which they are a member, employee, or affiliated with.¹⁹ This exemption applies only where processing is consistent with the institution's objectives and necessary to achieve its underlying aims and principles.

RIGHTS OF DATA SUBJECTS

The Ghanaian data law adopts eight core principles, including accountability, lawfulness of processing, specification of purpose, relevance, openness, data security, and data subject participation. These principles form the foundation of compliance obligations for technology platforms and service

¹⁷ Ibid s.60

¹⁸ Ibid s 37.

¹⁹ Ibid s.38

providers regarding the treatment of data subjects. The treatment of data subjects guaranteed under the GDPR are as follows:

- Data subjects have the right to be informed of the purpose for which their data is collected.²⁰ This requires data controllers to ensure transparency at the point of collection.
- Personal data must be processed lawfully, reasonably, and without infringing privacy rights²¹ including foreign data subjects²² within Ghana's jurisdiction.
- Personal data may only be processed where it is necessary, relevant, and not excessive in relation to the stated purpose.²³
- Consent is the primary basis for processing,²⁴ and processing without consent is allowed only where it is justified by law, contractual necessity, statutory duty, protection of legitimate interests, or overriding legitimate interests of the controller or a third party.
- Data subjects have the right to object to processing,²⁵ and the act requires processing to cease upon objection.²⁶
- Personal data should generally be collected directly from the data subject, and indirect collection is allowed only in limited circumstances, such as where data is public, consented to, or deliberately made public by the data subject.²⁷
- Where a data subject requires a controller to stop or avoid processing that causes or is likely to cause unwarranted damage or distress,²⁸ The controller must respond within 21 days, stating compliance or reasons for refusal.
- Where automated decisions or data harvesting occur, the data subject must be notified and allowed to request reconsideration.²⁹
- The data subject may require inaccurate or incomplete manual data to be rectified, blocked, erased, or destroyed.³⁰ This also applies where the data collected is incompatible with the

²⁰ Data Protection Act 2012 (Ghana) s 23

²¹ Ibid s.18(1)

²² Ibid s. 18(2)

²³ Ibid s. 19

²⁴ Ibid s.20(1)

²⁵ Ibid s. 20(2)

²⁶ Ibid s. 20(3)

²⁷ Ibid s. 21

²⁸ Ibid s.39

²⁹ Ibid s.41

³⁰ Ibid s.42

controller's legitimate purposes. The Commission may direct compliance following a justified complaint.

- The data subject may at any time require a controller to stop processing their data for marketing purposes;³¹ This right applies regardless of earlier consent.
- A data subject is entitled to compensation for damage or distress caused by a controller's breach of the Act.³²
- A data subject has a right to rectification, erasure, and destruction and may complain where personal data is inaccurate.³³ The commission may order that records be rectified to reflect the true factual position.

Together, these rights ensure transparency, lawful processing, proportionality, and meaningful control by the data subject.

AGENCY RESPONSIBLE FOR REGULATORY COMPLIANCE.

The **DPC** is established under the Act,³⁴ as the supervisory authority responsible for registration of data controllers, compliance regulation, investigation of complaints, and enforcement of sanctions. The DPC's objective is to protect individual privacy and data by regulating how personal data is processed. It does this by establishing procedures for the collection, use, storage, and disclosure of personal information.³⁵

The primary functions of the DPC are³⁶

- Implementing and monitoring compliance with the provisions of the Act.
- Making the administrative arrangements it considers appropriate for the discharge of its duties.
- Investigating any complaints under this Act and determining them in the manner the Commission considers fair.

³¹ Ibid s.40

³² Ibid s.43

³³ Ibid s. 44

³⁴ Ibid s.1

³⁵ Ibid s.2

³⁶ Ibid s.3

- Keeping and maintaining the data protection register.
- Carrying out audits to assess compliance with data protection laws and standards.
- Providing guidance, disseminating information, and collaborating with relevant entities to enhance understanding and awareness of data protection principles.
- Prescribing and enforcing appropriate remedies to address violations and mitigate the impact on an individual's privacy rights.

APPLICABILITY TO BUSINESSES

The Act applies to all public and private entities established in Ghana, as well as to foreign entities that process the personal data of Ghanaian citizens. Data that is merely in transit through Ghana is excluded from the scope.³⁷

RECOMMENDED SAFETY MEASURES

Under the Act, data controllers must use necessary security measures to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data. These measures should be both technical (e.g., encryption, access controls, etc.) and organisational (e.g., policies and managerial standards). If there is a reasonable suspicion of a security compromise, controllers must notify the Data Protection Commission (DPC) and, in some cases, the affected data subjects.³⁸

When the DPC finds a breach, it issues an enforcement notice.³⁹ directing the controller to stop, restrict, or change how data is processed. In urgent cases, the Commission can make them effective immediately.⁴⁰ The Commission can later amend or withdraw a notice, but controllers remain liable while it remains in effect.

If the Commission confirms non-compliance, it can issue an information notice requiring the controller to stop the unlawful processing.⁴¹ The Commission then issues written determinations where data processing breaches the Act or falls outside protected journalistic or artistic purposes.⁴² These determinations empower the Commission to enforce and penalise.

³⁷ Ibid s 4.

³⁸ Ibid s 28.

³⁹ Ibid s 75

⁴⁰ Ibid ss 75(6)-(7), s 76

⁴¹ Ibid s 77

⁴² Ibid ss. 78-79

COMPLIANCE OBLIGATIONS⁴³

Organisations must:

- Register as a data controller or processor with the DPC.⁴⁴
- Implement internal governance measures and principles.
- Maintain appropriate records, storage limitation, data minimisation, openness, integrity and security.
- Promptly inform, after discovery, both the regulator and the affected individual if personal data is accessed or obtained without authorisation.⁴⁵
- Take corrective steps to restore the security of their affected systems. after a breach or error.
- Entrench contracts with processors and safeguards for cross-border transfers.
- Respect data subject rights (to information, access, rectification, erasure, objection).

EXCEPTIONS

While this Act imposes stringent conditions on the processing of personal and sensitive data, it also provides certain exceptions to this requirement in the Act.

These circumstances include⁴⁶

- Where it is necessary to protect overriding public, institutional, or societal interests.
- Processing for national security, public order, safety, morality, and public interest.
- For crime prevention, prosecution, taxation, regulatory oversight, public health, education, and social work.
- Journalism, research, and statistics.
- Disclosures required by law or court order, e.g., domestic household activities, confidential references, armed forces operations.

⁴³ Ibid ss 22-34.

⁴⁴ Ibid s. 27

⁴⁵ Ibid s.31

⁴⁶ Ibid ss. 60 -74

- Information protected by legal professional privilege, subject in some cases to constitutional safeguards.
- Statutory exemptions apply to processing for national security, crime prevention, taxation, domestic household activities, and disclosures required by law or court order.

Penalties for non-compliance

Under the Act, the DPC is empowered to impose sanctions and other punitive measures to ensure compliance with the data protection provisions on defaulting organisations.

The DPC can issue the following compliance orders and administrative sanctions.

- Non-compliance with an enforcement or information notice constitutes a criminal offence and attracts penalties of up to 150 penalty units, imprisonment for up to one year, or both.⁴⁷
- Giving false or reckless information to the Commission also attracts the same penalties and is subject to a due diligence defence. Demands for personal or health records attract higher penalties of up to 250 penalty units or two years' imprisonment.

The enforcement infrastructure is supported by authorised officers with inspection and search powers, reinforcing the Commission's deterrent and corrective authority.⁴⁸

2. NIGERIA

LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Data Protection practices and rights in Nigeria are regulated and controlled by the **Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA), 2023**. The Act represents a significant legislative consolidation and expansion of earlier regulatory instruments. The Act provides a comprehensive statutory framework for the protection of personal data, designed to govern data processing, strengthen digital trust, provide governance of digital rights, and establish an independent commission to oversee data practices in Nigeria and enforce the data rights of its citizens.⁴⁹

⁴⁷ Ibid s.80

⁴⁸ Ibid s.81

⁴⁹ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023.

DEFINITION AND SCOPE⁵⁰

The NDPA adopts a broad definition in alignment with EU GDPR principles. These definitions encompass who a natural person is and sets out clearly the obligations owed to them by data controllers and processors.

The Act identifies three persons connected with Data: data processor, data controller, and data subjects, and it explicitly defines them. A **data controller** is an individual, private entity, public commission, agency or any other body who, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of processing of personal data while a **data processor** means an individual, private entity, public authority, or any other body, who processes personal data on behalf of or at the direction of a data controller or another data processor. The Act goes further to make a distinction by defining **data controllers or data processor of major importance** as those domiciled, resident, or operating in Nigeria and process or intending to process personal data of more than such number of data subjects who are within Nigeria, as the Commission may prescribe, or such other class of data controller or data processor that is processing personal data of particular value or significance to the economy, society or security of Nigeria as the Commission may designate. **Data subject** is an individual to whom personal data relates.

On issues relating to personal data and its enforcement, the Act is granted exclusive jurisdiction; this means that in matters directly or indirectly relating to the processing of personal data, the provisions of this Act shall prevail.⁵¹

PERSONAL DATA

Personal data under the NDPA includes any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, whether directly or indirectly identifiable. These include the following identifiers:

- Name, identification number
- Location data, online identifier
- Physical characteristics, physiological markers, and genetic data
- Psychological, cultural, social, and economic attributes

Nigeria Data

⁵¹ Ibid s.63

SENSITIVE PERSONAL DATA

Nigeria's statute specifies heightened protections for sensitive personal data. It defines such data to include:

- Genetic and biometric data, for uniquely identifying a natural person.
- Race or ethnic origin,
- Religious or similar beliefs, such as those reflecting conscience or philosophy,
- Health status; sex life,
- Political opinions or affiliations; trade union memberships,
- Other information prescribed by the Commission, as sensitive personal data.⁵²

RIGHTS OF A DATA SUBJECT

A data subject under NDPA has several rights which are provided for and must be complied with; they are as follows:

- Right to obtain confirmation that their personal data is processed and receive clear information on purposes, categories of data, recipients, retention periods, sources, and the existence and effects of automated decision making.⁵³
- A data subject may access their personal data and receive a copy in a commonly used electronic format, subject to reasonable cost recovery where provision imposes disproportionate expense.⁵⁴
- Right to rectification and correction of inaccurate data or deletion where correction is unsuitable, including data that is outdated, incomplete, or misleading.⁵⁵
- A data subject may object to processing, including profiling, and the controller must stop unless overriding public interest or legitimate grounds exist.⁵⁶

⁵² Ibid s. 30(2)

⁵³ Ibid s 34(1)(a)(i)-(viii)

⁵⁴ Ibid s 34(1)(a)-(b)

⁵⁵ Ibid s 34(1)(c)

⁵⁶ Ibid s 36(1)-(4)

- A data subject has the right to make a complaint with the Commission where processing infringes the Act.⁵⁷
- Subject to regulations, a data subject may receive personal data in a structured, commonly used, machine-readable format and transmit it to another controller, including direct transfer where technically feasible. This is the right to data portability.⁵⁸
- A data subject may require erasure without undue delay where data is no longer necessary or where no lawful basis for retention exists.⁵⁹
- A data subject has the right not to be subjected to automated processing that produces legal or similarly significant effects, except where necessary for a contract, authorised by law, or based on consent, with safeguards including human intervention, the right to express views, and to contest decisions.⁶⁰

AGENCY RESPONSIBLE FOR REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

The Act establishes the **Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC)** as an independent authority that exercises supervisory, investigative, corrective, and sanctioning powers in matters concerning data protection.

The Commission complements the work of statutory institutions of government in the common goal of safeguarding the privacy of natural persons.⁶¹

The NDPC is mandated to collaborate with stakeholders in achieving the objectives of the NDP Act, namely, to:

- Safeguard the rights of natural persons to data privacy.

⁵⁷ Ibid s 34(1)(a)(vi)

⁵⁸ Ibid s 38(1)-(3)

⁵⁹ Ibid ss 34(1)(d), 34(2)

⁶⁰ Ibid s 37(1)-(3)

⁶¹ see Section 37 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN, as amended); Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights; Article 17 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR); Section 8 of Child Rights Act; Part IV of Consumer Code of Practice Regulations (Nigerian Communications Commission); and Article 5.4 of Consumer Protection Regulation (Central Bank of Nigeria).

- Promote data processing practices that safeguard the security of personal data and the privacy of data subjects.
- Strengthen the legal foundations of the national digital economy and guarantee the participation of Nigeria in the regional and global economies through the beneficial and trusted use of personal data.

The NDPC may also issue directives, codes, or guidelines to govern its operations, budgeting, and governance. ⁶²

APPLICABILITY TO BUSINESSES

The Act applies to public and private-sector controllers and processors operating in Nigeria, as well as foreign entities processing the personal data of Nigerian data subjects, creating extraterritorial compliance exposure for global technology companies.⁶³ It binds non-resident entities processing data of individuals in Nigeria.

- The Act applies to personal data processing that affects the privacy rights of data subjects and falls within the regulatory oversight of the Commission.
- Even where exemptions exist, the Commission may issue guidance and safeguards to prevent breaches of core processing principles, particularly fairness and lawfulness.⁶⁴

SAFETY MEASURES

Under the NDPA, Controllers must implement privacy by design and by default, conduct data protection impact assessments for high-risk processing, implement risk-based security controls, and notify the NDPC of data breaches within prescribed timelines.

The Commission also maintains and publishes an online register of duly registered controllers and processors of major importance. ⁶⁵

⁶² Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, S. 65

⁶³ Ibid s 2.

⁶⁴ under ss 24 and 25 of the Act

⁶⁵ Ibid s 44

COMPLIANCE OBLIGATIONS

Organisations that determine the purpose and manner for processing data have certain rules under the Act that they must abide by.⁶⁶ These are usually referred to as compliance regulations.

1. Controllers and processors must handle personal data lawfully, fairly, transparently, securely, and only to the extent and duration necessary, while ensuring accuracy and accountability in compliance with a statutory duty of care.⁶⁷ Any further processing must remain compatible with the original purpose, with public interest research and archiving expressly treated as permissible extensions.
2. Processing is lawful only where it is grounded in a recognised legal basis, including consent, contractual necessity, legal obligation, protection of vital interests, public interest, or legitimate interests.⁶⁸
3. Controllers shall bear the burden of demonstrating that valid consent was obtained, and consent must be clear, informed, freely given, affirmative, and capable of withdrawal, with silence or inactivity having no legal effect.⁶⁹
4. Before collecting personal data, controllers must clearly inform data subjects of their identity, lawful basis for processing, purposes, recipients, retention period, data subject rights, complaint mechanisms, and any use of automated decision making. Where data is collected indirectly, the same disclosure obligations apply unless providing the information is impossible or would involve disproportionate effort.⁷⁰
5. Where processing relies on consent, controllers must obtain consent from a parent or legal guardian and apply reasonable age verification measures. These requirements do not apply where processing is necessary to protect vital interests, provide education,

⁶⁶ Ibid s 29

⁶⁷ Ibid s 24

⁶⁸ Ibid s 25

⁶⁹ Ibid s 26

⁷⁰ Ibid s.27

medical or social care, support court proceedings, and all processing must remain consistent with child protection law.⁷¹

6. Controllers of major importance are required to appoint a suitably qualified Data Protection Officer to provide compliance advice, monitor internal practices, and act as the liaison with the Commission.⁷² The Commission may also license independent experts to monitor, audit, and report on compliance with the Act and its subsidiary instruments.⁷³

Other obligations include:

- Embedding privacy by design and privacy by default across all processing activities.
- Mapping processing operations and applying the principles of lawfulness, purpose limitation, data minimisation, storage limitation, and security.
- Recording and justifying the lawful basis for each processing activity.
- Implementing risk-based technical and organisational security measures.
- Identifying high-risk processing activities and conducting data protection impact assessments and compliance audits.
- Maintaining breach detection procedures and notifying the Commission within statutory timelines.
- Registering with the Commission where required.
- Appointing a Data Protection Officer where required and defining oversight and reporting responsibilities.
- Executing binding contracts with processors, monitoring compliance, and allocating responsibilities.

⁷¹ Ibid s.31

⁷² Ibid s.32

⁷³ Ibid s.33

- Establishing and documenting lawful cross-border data transfer mechanisms and safeguards.

Finally, when a data controller reaches the legal data processing threshold of 1,000 data subjects within six (6) months and 2,000 data subjects within twelve (12) months must submit its audit report to the Commission.⁷⁴ The deadline for filing the said report was 15 March 2024.

The filing process is facilitated by approved Data Protection Compliance Organisations (DPCOs). These organisations are registered on a list maintained by the Commission and work on behalf of their clients to support them in their compliance processing.

EXCEPTIONS

Lawful processing of personal data requires a legal basis such as consent, contract, legal obligation, vital interests, public interest,⁷⁵ and specific rules for research and cross-border transfers (typically consent or adequacy).⁷⁶ Processing cross-border transfers without consent is permitted when necessary to meet legal obligations, the public interest, national security, or the protection of vital interests, subject to proportionality and safeguards.

Some of these exceptional circumstances include:⁷⁷

- Where the transfer is necessary to perform a contract with the data subject or to take steps requested by the data subject before entering a contract.
- Where the transfer benefits only the data subject, consent is not reasonably practicable to obtain, and the data subject would likely consent if asked.
- The transfer is necessary for important public interest reasons recognised by law.
- The transfer is necessary to establish, exercise, or defend legal claims.
- The transfer is necessary to protect the life or fundamental interests of the data subject or another person where the data subject cannot give consent.

⁷⁴ Ibid s 4.1, para 6-7

⁷⁵ Ibid s.24(4)

⁷⁶ Ibid s.25

⁷⁷ Ibid s.43

REGISTRATION AND FEES APPLICABLE⁷⁸

- Data controllers and processors of major importance must register with the Commission within six months of the Act's commencement or upon attaining that status.
- Registration requires disclosure of core operational details, including organisational and DPO identities, categories of personal data and data subjects, processing purposes, recipients, processors acting on the entity's behalf, intended cross-border transfers, and risk and security measures, plus any additional information the Commission requires.
- Any significant change to registered information must be notified to the Commission within sixty days.
- The Commission may prescribe registration fees or levies payable by controllers and processors of major importance.

ENFORCEMENT AND PENALTIES

The Act provides for administrative fines, corrective orders, suspension of processing activities, and judicial remedies, with penalties tiered by organisational size and severity of non-compliance. Nigeria recognises a private right of action for data subjects and has imposed administrative fines on multinational technology firms for non-compliance. i.e., the \$220 million fine on Meta in July 2024.⁷⁹

The enforcement mechanisms under the act are outlined as follows:

1. COMPLAINTS AND INVESTIGATIONS⁸⁰

A data subject may file a complaint with the Commission against any decision, action, or inaction by a controller or processor that breaches the Act or subsidiary legislation. The Commission may investigate non-frivolous complaints or commence investigations on its own initiative where a violation is suspected or likely.

For investigations, the Commission may compel attendance, require documents, demand sworn statements, and obtain access to electronic or physical records in readable formats.

⁷⁸ Ibid s. 44

⁷⁹ Nigeria Data Protection Commission, 'Official Guidance and Regulatory Materials' <https://ndpc.gov.ng> accessed 14 January 2026.

⁸⁰ Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023, s,46

2. COMPLIANCE ORDERS ⁸¹

Where a violation is established or likely to occur, the Commission may issue a written compliance order. Orders may include warnings, directions to comply with the Act or data subject rights, or cease-and-desist orders halting unlawful processing.

Each order must specify the breached provisions, corrective measures, timelines, and the right to judicial review.

3. ENFORCEMENT ORDERS AND SANCTIONS⁸²

Following an investigation, the Commission may impose enforcement orders or sanctions in addition to any criminal liability. Sanctions may require remediation, compensation to affected data subjects, disgorgement of profits, or payment of penalties or remedial fees.

Maximum penalties depend on status:

- up to the higher maximum amount for controllers or processors of significant importance, or the standard maximum amount for others.
- the higher maximum amount is the greater of N10,000,000 or 2 percent of annual gross revenue, while the standard maximum amount is the greater of N2,000,000 or 2 percent of annual gross revenue.

In setting sanctions, the Commission must consider gravity, duration, intent, scale of harm, cooperation, and data sensitivity

4. JUDICIAL REVIEW ⁸³

Any person dissatisfied with a Commission order may seek judicial review within thirty days.

5. CIVIL REMEDIES ⁸⁴

Data subjects who suffer injury, loss, or harm may pursue civil damages against the controller or processor.

⁸¹ Ibid s 47

⁸² Ibid s 48

⁸³ Ibid s. 50

⁸⁴ Ibid s.51

6. FORFEITURE ⁸⁵

Courts may order forfeiture of proceeds linked to data protection offences under the proceeds of crime regime.

LIABILITY FOR NON-COMPLIANCE

Failure to comply with a compliance order constitutes a criminal offence, punishable by fines up to the applicable maximum amount, imprisonment for up to one year, or both. ⁸⁶

Corporate entities and their principal officers may be held jointly liable, subject to due diligence defences, and controllers and processors are vicariously liable for acts of agents or employees. ⁸⁷

The NDPC's notice also provides for a set of specific sanctions in the event of non-compliance with the filing of the Compliance Audit Report (CAR). The penalties provided fall into two categories: financial and procedural or reputational.

The data controller or processor must therefore:

1. Remedy the breach.
2. Pay compensation to the data subject who has suffered harm, loss, or damage because of the breach.
3. Account for any profits made because of the breach.
4. Pay a penalty or repair costs.

3. SIERRA LEONE

STATUS OF DATA PROTECTION REGULATION

Sierra Leone currently lacks an enacted data protection statute; Privacy protection derives primarily from constitutional provisions under **Article 22**⁸⁸ which provides a foundation for personal privacy and confidentiality.

⁸⁵ Ibid s.52

⁸⁶ Ibid s.49

⁸⁷ Ibid s.53

⁸⁸ Constitution of Sierra Leone 1991, art 22.

The **Data Protection and Right to Access Information Bill, 2025**⁸⁹ has undergone nationwide consultation and validation. This proposed law aims to establish a comprehensive data protection framework with institutional oversight and align with GDPR principles. It also defines categories of personal and sensitive data. The minister for information clarified that the purpose of the law is not punitive but protective. He reaffirmed that the Ministry's goal is to ensure the law promotes trust, accountability, and data security across both public and private institutions.

According to officials, the bill is modelled on global best practices, drawing from the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the African Union's Malabo Convention. Once passed, it will position Sierra Leone among countries with modern digital security frameworks, while boosting investor confidence and international cooperation.

REGULATORY GAPS

In the absence of enacted legislation, compliance obligations for businesses remain undefined, and contractual or sectoral instruments fill the regulatory vacuum. This creates significant legal uncertainty regarding compliance obligations, enforcement exposure, and data subject rights. **The 2023 Cyber Security and Crime Act** is the only relevant statute currently in effect in the country.

IMPLICATIONS

Weak data protection enables harassment, abuse, and the non-consensual sharing of intimate images, compounding existing patterns of cyber violence. In the absence of adequate legal safeguards, affected groups lack meaningful remedies, reinforcing online silencing and exclusion. Consequently, disadvantaged groups such as women and children are more likely to be hit with fake news and hate speech, harassment, abuse, and the non-consensual sharing of intimate images and their data exploited for discriminatory or defamatory purposes. In a society where gender-based violence is already a serious issue, the lack of data protection rapidly increases such risks, creating a digital space where people feel unsafe and silenced.⁹⁰

⁸⁹ Draft Data Protection and Right to Access Information Bill 2025 (Sierra Leone) <https://moice.gov.sl/nationwide-consultations-begin-on-sierra-leones-first-data-protection-law> accessed 14 January 2026.

⁹⁰ Daniel Sawaneh, *The Unseen Victims: How Sierra Leone's Lack of a Data Protection Regime Is Endangering Its Future* (SierraLII, 3 March 2025) <https://sierralii.gov.sl/articles/2025-03-03/daniel-sawaneh-the-unseen-victims-how-sierra-leones-lack-of-a-data-protection-regime-is-endangering-its-future> accessed 24 January 2026.

4. GAMBIA

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

The **Data Protection and Privacy Bill of The Gambia, 2024**, has been passed by the National Assembly and awaits presidential assent, marking a pivotal transition toward robust data governance. The Act establishes a comprehensive framework for lawful processing and protection of rights.⁹¹

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Data subjects are defined under the act as individuals whose information is handled by data processors and, by so doing, gain robust rights under the law. These include:

- The right to be informed about data usage, access to one's data.⁹²
- Right to rectification, erasure, and restriction of processing.⁹³
- Right to object.⁹⁴
- Right not to be subject to automated decision-making.⁹⁵
- Right to obtain assistance from the Commission.⁹⁶
- Representation of the data subject.⁹⁷
- Right to remedy.⁹⁸

Mechanisms for exercising these rights are mandated, and controllers are required to respond within one (1) month, extendable under certain conditions.⁹⁹ The act also prohibits processing that infringes on privacy without justification, echoing constitutional protections.

⁹¹ Tech Hive Advisory Africa, 'Review of Gambia's Personal Data Protection and Privacy Act 2025' (2025) <https://www.techhiveadvisory.africa/insights/review-of-gambias-personal-data-protection-and-privacy-act-2025> accessed 14 January 2026.

⁹² Data Protection and Privacy Bill of the Gambia, 2024, s.9

⁹³ Ibid s.10

⁹⁴ Ibid s.11

⁹⁵ Ibid s.12

⁹⁶ Ibid s.13

⁹⁷ Ibid s.14

⁹⁸ Ibid s.15

⁹⁹ Ibid s.22

CORE PROVISIONS¹⁰⁰

PERSONAL DATA: the act broadly defines personal data as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, including identifiers such as names, biometric details, and online behaviour.

SENSITIVE DATA: includes any form of data that includes health records, political opinions, biometric, financial, and religious beliefs. This class of data receives heightened safeguards, requiring explicit consent or a legal basis for processing.

GROUND FOR DATA PROCESSING

The Act establishes lawful bases for processing, guarantees data subject rights, including access, rectification, portability, erasure, and objection, and mandates documentation of processing activities. Therefore,

- Controllers must obtain explicit consent for sensitive personal data unless a statutory exception applies.¹⁰¹
- Control can only process data where consent, contractual necessity, legal obligation, vital interests, public interest, or legitimate interests apply.¹⁰²
- Controllers must also document processing activities and ensure purpose limitation and data minimisation.

WHAT BUSINESSES DOES IT APPLY TO?

The Act applies to **public and private entities** that process personal data within The Gambia or target data subjects in The Gambia.¹⁰³ The act also addresses structural challenges, such as limited digital inclusion in rural areas and government use of data in public services. It prescribes awareness campaigns and capacity-building for small businesses, recognising the nation's budding digital economy.¹⁰⁴

¹⁰⁰ Ibid. Parts II–IV.

¹⁰¹ Ibid s.7

¹⁰² Ibid s.6

¹⁰³ Ibid s.5

¹⁰⁴ Ibid part ii & x

Cross-border transfers are also restricted to jurisdictions that offer adequate protection or safeguards, such as standard contractual clauses, to prevent data flows to high-risk countries.

REGULATORY AUTHORITY

Oversight functions are assigned to the National Data Protection Commission.¹⁰⁵ with expanded enforcement and investigative powers. This includes powers to investigate breaches, issue enforcement notices, and impose administrative and criminal sanctions, including penalties for unlawful data trading and concealment of breaches.¹⁰⁶ Compliance Architecture.¹⁰⁷

Controllers and processors must document processing activities, implement security measures proportionate to risk, perform DPIAs (Deep Packet Inspections) for high-risk operations, conduct impact assessments, and notify breaches within defined timelines.

Controllers must also appoint a Data Protection Officer where required.

Controllers, who determine the purposes of processing, must conduct data protection impact assessments for high-risk activities, appoint a data protection officer if necessary, and notify breaches to the authority within 72 hours. Processors, acting on controllers' behalf, must ensure secure handling through contracts that outline their core responsibilities.¹⁰⁸

PENALTIES

The Act provides for administrative sanctions, financial penalties, and criminal liability for serious violations. The prescribed criminal sanctions for unlawful processing, data sales, and concealment of data breaches are significant, including imprisonment for up to five years.¹⁰⁹ It also imposes administrative fines of up to 4% of annual global turnover for serious violations.¹¹⁰, signalling strong compliance expectations.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid. Part VII.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid s.40-44

¹⁰⁷ Ibid s.24-27

¹⁰⁸ Ibid s.25

¹⁰⁹ Ibid s.46

¹¹⁰ Ibid s.45

5. LIBERIA

REGULATORY STATUS

Liberia lacks a dedicated data protection statute or supervisory authority. Constitutional privacy protections exist, but there is no formal statutory mechanism governing the processing, security, or transfer of personal data.¹¹¹

Tech sector entities in Liberia must derive compliance requirements from contractual obligations, sectoral regulations, or broader human rights norms until a formal legal framework is enacted.

IMPLICATIONS FOR TECHNOLOGY BUSINESSES

The absence of statutory guidance creates regulatory vacuums, heightens compliance risk, and undermines the enforceability of data subject rights, posing elevated risk for digital service providers operating in or from Liberia.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS TABLE

Jurisdiction	Statute in Force	Independent Regulatory Body	Cross-Border Rules	DPIA* Required	Data Localisation Requirement
Ghana	Yes	Yes	Broad; Partial	Implicit	Yes
Nigeria	Yes	Yes	Extraterritorial	Yes	Yes
Gambia	Act passed and pending assent	Proposed	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sierra Leone	A draft bill has been proposed	Proposed	No	No	No
Liberia	No	No	No	No	No

Data Protection Impact Assessment*

¹¹¹ Constitution of Liberia.

INSTITUTIONAL LANDSCAPE OF DATA PROTECTION AUTHORITIES IN AFRICA¹¹²

Effective data protection systems depend not only on statutory design but on the existence, independence, and operational capacity of supervisory authorities responsible for enforcement, guidance, and cross-border cooperation.¹¹³ More than thirty African states have established data protection authorities mandated to oversee compliance, investigate breaches, issue guidance, and enforce statutory obligations.¹¹⁴ Although enforcement capacity varies significantly, these authorities serve as the primary interface between legislative requirements and practical implementation for both public bodies and the private sector.

Within West Africa, institutional maturity closely tracks legislative development. Ghana's Data Protection Commission is fully operational and performs core functions, including controller registration, compliance monitoring, and enforcement of the Data Protection Act. Nigeria's National Data Protection Commission demonstrates a higher degree of regulatory specificity and enforcement engagement, including active participation in regional regulatory cooperation frameworks, signalling an emerging commitment to cross-border enforcement coordination.¹¹⁵

By contrast, Sierra Leone and Liberia lack fully operational data protection authorities, reflecting the absence of comprehensive statutory frameworks. This institutional gap limits oversight, constrains enforcement, and leaves organisations without authoritative regulatory guidance. Gambia, on the other hand, has designated its Information Commission as the supervisory authority under the 2025 Data Protection Legislation. However, its regulatory role remains transitional pending the commencement of the Act.¹¹⁶

Nigeria's Act shares similarities with Gambia's regulation in fines and cross-border rules, but places greater emphasis on economic proportionality. The Act permits penalties of up to 2% of annual turnover, which is lower than Gambia's 4%, potentially making Gambia's system more punitive.

¹¹² Open Government Partnership, 'Data Protection in Africa: A Look at OGP Member Progress' (2021) <https://www.opengovpartnership.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/OGP-Data-Protection-Report.pdf> accessed 14 January 2026.

¹¹³ Data Protection Africa Portal <https://dataprotection.africa> accessed 14 January 2026.

¹¹⁴ Ibid

¹¹⁵ *Business and Financial Times* (Ghana), 'Navigating Cross Border Data Protection: Evaluating Ghana's Legal Framework Against International Standards' (28 March 2025) <https://thebfronline.com/2025/03/28/navigating-cross-border-data-protection-evaluating-our-legal-framework-against-international-standards> accessed 14 January 2026.

¹¹⁶ Ibid

CONCLUSION

West Africa's data protection landscape reflects uneven regulatory maturity. Nigeria provides the most comprehensive statutory framework, while Ghana, despite its progressive framework, continues to face significant enforcement challenges. Gambia, on the other hand, is nearing operational maturity, and Sierra Leone and Liberia face urgent legislative deficits. Harmonised reform and capacity building are essential to support digital trust, protect rights, and sustain growth in the technology sector. Results show that only Ghana and Nigeria have comprehensive data protection laws that comply with Article 2 of the ECOWAS Supplementary Act on Personal Data Protection and with the ISO/IEC 29100:2011 standard.

In conclusion, while Africa is making strides in developing data protection regulations, the journey towards harmonisation and alignment with global standards is ongoing. Further reforms and initiatives are needed to ensure a cohesive and effective data protection landscape across the continent.¹¹⁷

¹¹⁷ Makulilo (n 4).

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